
DEVELOPING ULTRA-LITE ML MODELS FOR CRASH DETECTION IN NOISY ENVIRONMENTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on developing a novel machine-learning (ML) solution on edge-devices, operating in high-noise environments, to detect major faults and events (such as crashes). Every year, thousands of people are subject to bicycle crashes that result from motor-vehicle accidents, poor conditions, etc. A more reliable and on-site anomaly detection will allow for quicker responses in emergencies, helping reduce long-term injuries. Currently, statistical analysis models are being used, but they struggle to detect such anomalies in noisy environments, leading to false alarms. As a solution, an IoT edge device was developed that deploys an ultra-lite ML model to better detect crashes, then notify an emergency contact. To tackle the lack of open-source bicycle crash vibration data, this paper also proposes a novel bicycle crash simulation methodology, utilizing bicycle self-stabilizing properties, to get the data for training. The simple and cost-efficient crash-simulation methodology devised is shown to be rather effective, circumventing the project's cost and other safety-related limitations. The prototype consists of a microcontroller, an IMU, and a GPS. A separate device was also developed to do the data collection and data storage. An ultra-lite ML (<10 KB) was trained, tested, and developed in an iterative process. In a comparison with two statistical analysis models, the ML model had a 130% improvement in accuracy.

Keywords Machine Learning · Embedded Systems · Internet of Things · Crash Detection · Microcontrollers · tinyML

1 Introduction

In recent years, the integration of smart transportation with existing infrastructure has grown increasingly common. Particularly with the advent of e-bicycles and e-scooters, many cities have started to incorporate these technologies into their existing transportation frameworks. However, this rise in personal transportation has also resulted in a significant increase in injuries related to e-bike and motorized scooter accidents nationwide. For instance, e-bike related injuries saw a 21% increase between 2021 and 2022 [1]. This is particularly acute in developing countries, where inexpensive personal transportation, such as bicycles, is prevalent: 90% of road traffic-bicycle related mortalities occur in these regions [2].

To address this problem, studies have proposed various solutions that attempt to detect a crash and then automatically notify emergency contacts in hopes of reducing the time required for emergency medical services to arrive at the sight. Most modern solutions can be categorized into 3 sets: onsite ML based detection, onsite statistical analysis-based detection, and cloud-ML based detection. Each has its own advantages and disadvantages.

Most crash detection devices typically utilize statistical analysis and sensor fusion based algorithms, which are generally computationally inexpensive and thus easily integrable into existing infrastructure. However, due to poor design choices, these devices are often bulky and produce plenty of false alarms. For example, researchers in Bangladesh made a device

that consists of a Raspberry Pi 3, Arduino Uno, an IMU, GPS, and a SIM808 [3]. Their detection algorithm works by computing the angle the bike makes with the ground, and if it exceeds 45 degrees, then the Raspberry Pi sends a signal to the Arduino that a crash was detected. They claim that their algorithm has an accuracy close to 100%, however, when this was recreated in our crash simulation methodology, the algorithm performed very poorly. This is due to a few reasons; first, the acceleration that is experienced on the bike while in movement is high in noise. Thus, sensors like accelerometers will contain high amounts of noise in the output signal. For example, Figure 1 below is a graph of accelerometer measurements (on the z-axis) collected in our crash simulation methodology:

Figure 1: Accelerometer measurements of negative and positive crashes, Z-axis.

In Figure 1, the negative (orange) trace represents when the bike is moving in the environment without stimuli (crash) or normal movement. And the left_crash (blue) is when the bike receives an external stimulus from the left. Since this environment is high in noise, it is hard to distinguish between a spike that might indicate a crash, and one that is noise. While the researchers attempted to attack this problem by utilizing a complimentary filter (a sensor fusion algorithm that will combine the gyroscope and accelerometer measurements), which is somewhat effective, the underlining algorithm (based off tilt-angle alone) is not an effective method to detect bicycle crashes, as shown in Figure 2:

$$\text{rollAngle} = \omega_{\text{gyro}} \cdot \theta_{\text{gyro}} + \omega_{\text{acc}} \cdot \theta_{\text{acc}}$$

Gyroscope coefficient (usually > 0.5)
Accelerometer coefficient (usually < 0.5)

$$\omega_{\text{gyro}} + \omega_{\text{acc}} = 1$$

Figure 2: Representation of roll angle computation.

Figure 3: Accelerometer measurements of a crash and fall, Y-axis.

For instance, a simple fall, such as when a child drops a bicycle to one side, would produce similar acceleration and tilt angle readings as a crash, yet it is not the same. However, an unmanned bike, falling to the ground from a fall, is not the same as a bike crashing. These problems are mostly unaddressed in this study. Thus, a tilt angle cannot possibly differentiate between a crash and the bike falling over. Methods like this will produce false alarms, which can become a problem for local authorities. Furthermore, the study claiming that this method can have an accuracy close to 100%, is an indication that their testing and validation methodology isn't accurate. This is mostly due to the limitations and struggles related to simulating a bicycle crash. However, we have come up with a novel bicycle crash methodology that attempts to circumvent these limitations.

Apart from statistical analysis-based approaches, there have also been proposed solutions which involve ML algorithms on mobile devices. A 2023 study by Lui et al. demonstrates that a more complicated algorithm can perform about 3.8 times better than accelerometer-based heuristic models. But a device which is reliant on a mobile device isn't an effective long-term solution, as not only do majority of bicyclists ride without their phones, but also, most people in developing countries don't have access to phones capable enough to efficiently run these ML algorithms. Plus, this isn't an energy efficient solution, as the battery on the phone cannot sustain long periods of intensive computation. There are also solutions which rely on cloud-based ML, which isn't a reliable solution as a constant cloud connection is required (which isn't always feasible in regions with limited connectivity).

In summary, a more reliable form of crash detection is via Artificial Intelligence (AI) and ML based algorithms. But due to computation restrictions, most rely impractical applications (like phones or cloud computing). As an alternative, we propose a compromised, microcontroller-based implementation of an ultra-lite ML model, capable of operating independently on the device, providing a balance between reliability and resource efficiency.

To address the challenge of this onsite crash detection, we designed, trained, and optimized an ultra-lightweight machine learning (ML) model. The prototype was realized through a comprehensive hardware-software integration, including 3D printing of the case, microcontroller integration, sensor deployment, software implementation, and communication systems. A development platform and workflow were also conceived, encompassing physical experimentation, data collection, and model training while also circumventing the cost and safety limitations. This data was made open-source so further validation and testing is possible, with a well-developed, all encompassing, dataset.

2 Project Purpose

I developed a full-scope implementation (from concept on paper to a functioning prototype) for bicycle crash detection on resource-limited edge devices. I designed, trained, and built an ultra-lite machine-learning (ML) model to carry out the

detection task onsite. I also created a hardware-software implementation of the prototype (including 3D-printing of the case, integration of microcontroller, sensors, software deployments, and communications). For doing all of these, I also conceived a development platform and workflow; including a physical experimenting and testing platform, data collection, and model training.

My overarching goal has been to develop and implement on-device anomaly detection with ML at edge systems in “noisy” environments. The bicycle-crash-detection application has been chosen (after months of searching and thinking) for various reasons including:

- demonstration practicality (e.g. cost, access to platforms, testing difficulty, etc.),
- high levels of noise in bicycle terrains, and
- potential various solutions with apparent health safety benefits (e.g. smart cities and transportation involving e-bikes and e-scooters, elderly care, veteran care, robotics, industrial automation, and so on).

3 Methods

This paper focuses on developing a cost effective, onsite crash detection system that deploys an ultra-lite ML model. Achieving this requires the creation of a novel, comprehensive dataset for training purposes, as well as a structured development process for designing, training, and tuning the ML models.

3.1 Methods: Device Design Constraints

For the prototype to meet the addressed the problems discussed above; it needs to meet several specific design requirements.

This device is meant to be constantly attached to the bicycle. Any form of attachment, like on helmets or worn are unreliable as not all users will constantly wear helmets or a specific suit. So, a device that is constantly on the bicycle is required, to increase reliability. But this comes with it’s own power constraints. So, to sustain this long-term computation, the device requires a relatively low-power computer that is powerful enough to run ML models. The device must also be low-cost, as it needs to be widely accessible for most ranges of economic status.

To minimize user inconvenience while riding the bicycle, the device should be preferable, in a small form factor. This will also decrease the stresses on the bike mounts while exerting high G’s, this will possibly reduce the possibility of the device falling off the bike while riding.

After crashes are detected, the device needs to notify an emergency contact. While using a cloud connection is a solution, a constant connection might not always be possible, when utilizing LoRa or other long-range technologies. So the device must also have LTE capabilities. Furthermore, the device should also have BLE capabilities, as this would be required to communicate with the device during data collection.

While the main Micro Controller Unit (MCU) should be fast enough to run ML models, usually, this operation will use up all the computer’s resources. So, running any arithmetic calculations, other than those required for the ML model, shouldn’t be a necessity. Thus, to minimize this statistical computation, the crash detection algorithm must prioritize using raw accelerometer measurements.

3.1.1 Solution Ideas and Objectives

- Are relatively small NN (Neural Network) models capable of distinguishing features in high-noise environments?
- Can these models be further developed (e.g. innovative model-reductions) to minimize their implementation footprint without reducing detection accuracy?
- Can I develop a test platform that provides an effective way to design, simulate crashes, and test these models?

3.1.2 Methods: Limiting Factors

Regarding the effective deployment of Edge-ML solutions, there comes some significant factors that limit effective deployment. Firstly, running ML models require high computational complexity: when running inference, millions of expensive floating-point operations are needed to classify each input data point. Along with this, ML models also add to the program’s memory footprint: large amounts of weights, biases, and activations are limited by on-chip memory and bandwidth constraints. These two constraints leads to the final one; running these models will require and demand more

power: due to the high computational complexities of ML models, when running inference, a lot of power is consumed which could easily limit the battery life.

3.2 Methods: Methodology

To address the challenges caused from the faulty and insufficient data when training the model, a data collection methodology was designed. While some data on bicycle crashes might exist, there currently isn't any open-source data that provides accelerometer (and other inertial cues) data of real-time bicycle crashes (whether thru simulations or other means). Thus, a cost-efficient data-collection methodology is necessary to obtain this new data.

However, this data collection methodology is time consuming, so prior to training the model, an extensive data augmentation is required. On top of this, there are dozens of intricate hyperparameters that need to be tuned and experimented with to optimize the model. The final dataset was expanded to over 3000 points, from an initial 50, in data augmentation.

3.2.1 Methodology: Model Testing Methodology

To test these models, I initially had to deploy each model-revision out in the field, which was very labor-intensive and time consuming. So, a testing methodology was developed that consists of three stages: first, the model is evaluated via its confusion matrix and other statistical measurements that can take place during/after training on the personal computer; if a model performed sufficiently, it was then deployed on the device and crashes were simulated in software, by feeding in pre-collected crash data; finally, to make sure the model can perform in real time, the model is deployed on the device, on the bicycle when crashes are simulated; however, this crash simulation isn't the full impact as this would still be cost effective. Instead, an impact was simulated by providing an impact to the bike, when stationary. This solution has proved to be an efficient solution as it contains hierarchical thresholds to model validation, that will help save time when having to compare dozens of models.

Figure 4, is a block diagram, to help visualize this process:

Figure 4: Block diagram of development methodology.

3.2.2 Methodology: Data Collection Methodology

Given the absence of open-source bicycle crash data, we had to develop our own crash dataset. However, this process (if simulated with actual crashes which will involve motor-vehicles and human participants) is time-consuming, expensive,

and most importantly, unsafe. As a solution, a data collection technique was developed which will involve a test bike, a data collection device, and an impact that will be applied to the bike to simulate the “crash”.

Most prior testing techniques involved the bike standing upright, stationary. However, this is a very poor simulation of bicycle movement, which will drastically change the inertial cues supplied to the model. So, as a solution, this technique utilizes bicycle self-stabilizing properties to allow for the bike to stay upright. To simulate movement and moderate to high speeds, this technique utilizes hills and slopes that will allow the bikes to naturally accelerate to necessary speeds. In simple terms, the methodology works like this: the bike will be at the top of a hill, and an experimenter will push the bike, giving it an initial velocity. Due to the gravitational force, the bike will naturally accelerate down the hill. The crashes were simulated by accelerating an unmanned bicycle downhill and then instigating an anomaly after sufficient speed was achieved. A kick to the bike’s frame was tested as the safest and most easily impactful method.

Figure 5: Bicycle Kinematics

[4]

Figure 6: Front view of Bicycle

[5]

3.2.3 Methodology: Crash Simulation Methodology

This technique simulates movement and moderate to high speeds by using hills/slopes, allowing the bike to naturally accelerate. Bicycles are self-stabilizing (once the bike has achieved a threshold velocity), due to the bike's intrinsic kinematics. There are three main reasons why bikes can behave like this: the angle of the front wheel axis, the position of the handlebars, and a small amount of gyroscopic stability. Referring to Figure 4, the front wheel axis (and its extension) lies in front of the point at which the wheel touches the ground. So once the bike starts to tilt, the normal force from the ground will cause the front wheel to turn in the direction of the tilt, effectively steering the bike. As in Figure 5, the weight from the handlebars will magnify this effect. And lastly, once the bicycle starts to reach sufficient speeds, the wheels provide a small amount of gyroscopic stability.

To control the data collection, the device implemented a BLE connection to interface with a phone. By manually controlling when data collection should start and stop, only the crash signals were collected. Three types of negative data were also collected: the bicycle moving down the hill with no impact, the bicycle traversing various terrains, and an impact when the bicycle is at rest. About 25 crashes were collected from each side (total of 50); around 140 negative data points were collected, which includes riding around with a rider, the bicycle rolling down the hill with no rider, and around 30 fall datapoints, which are impacts (not crash impacts but pushes that simulate a fall) when the bike is stationary.

Below, in Figure 7, is an example of how the accelerometer data is represented.

```
X: , Y: , Z:  
0.85,-0.28,0.5,  
0.44,0.08,0.09,  
-0.72,-0.29,1.77,  
0.03,-0.06,-0.14,  
0.37,-0.14,0.85,  
-0.26,0.17,-0.22,  
0.22,-0.66,0.07,  
-0.07,0.15,0.01,  
-0.55,2.6,0.21,  
-0.59,0.44,-0.9,  
-0.36,-0.26,-0.69,  
0.29,0.11,-0.23,  
-0.1,-0.35,-0.22,  
0.28,-0.06,0.04,  
0.48,-0.85,0.66,  
0.3,0.17,1.71,  
1.94,0.87,0.65,  
-0.25,-0.93,-0.15,  
-0.36,-0.24,-0.1,  
-0.05,-0.43,0.42,  
-0.79,-1.25,1.57,  
-1.9,-0.06,3.49,
```

Figure 7: Example of collected 3-axis accelerometer data

3.3 Design: Data Collection Device

The device that will be used to collect the data needs to have a few components: the main microcontroller, and Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), and a data storage device. The main microcontroller will be a Particle Boron LTE microcontroller. This device was specifically chosen, due to its LTE, BLE, Flash, and 32-bit processing capabilities. The Particle Boron LTE features a Nordic nRF52840 SoC, which is an ARM Cortex-M4F 32-bit processor, running at 64MHz. The Boron has built in 256KB RAM, 1MB flash, and on-board additional 4MB of SPI flash. While this extra flash unit was originally used for the IMU data storage, these flash devices get increasingly less efficient.

I used a perfboard to build the data collection prototype, containing a Particle Boron LTE microcontroller, a LSM9DS1 9-axis IMU, and a SD Card module (used for the onsite storage of the data). I soldered the devices by hand, and it was developed in a modular system. I also designed a 3D case in Onshape, that allowed for a more robust deployment of the PCB. The case was designed considering the vibration and other environments the device would face. Also, a custom attachment was designed for the case, so that it could attach to the bicycle. A total of 11 different versions were tested for this system.

3D Case
for
Perfboard

3D
Designed
Bike mount
for Case

Figure 8: Data Collection Device & 3D printed Case mounted on Bike Frame

Figure 9: Schematic of Data Collection Device

3.4 Design: Application Prototype

Using many ideas from the data collecting device, I engineered another system for the final prototype. On a separate perfboard, and in a modular style, a Particle Boron and LSM9DS1 were soldered. A separate, more lightweight and compact, 3D enclosing was designed as well. An Adafruit Ultimate GPS module was also added so the device can send over its location to an emergency contact when a crash is detected. The final prototype was designed in the most compact way possible, to reduce size and weight.

Button to
stop SMS

Cellular
Antenna for
SMS
messaging

Battery
Connection

Figure 10: Prototype Mounted on Bike with 3D Designed Case

Figure 11: Schematic of application prototype

3.5 Model Architecture

Various model architectures (including RNN, LSTM, GRU, CNN, and multi-layer perceptron) were compared across three trials, which simple improvements to each model across trials. We found that while the GRU had the highest accuracy, the CNN had the highest accuracy to size ratio which means on average, the CNN will be more size efficient than the GRU.

Figure 12: Various model metrics, trial 1

Figure 13: Various model metrics, trial 2

Figure 14: Various model metrics, trial 3

Figure 15 is a bar graph of the averaged accuracies and losses across the five models.

Figure 15: Average metrics for various models

And Figure 16 represents the accuracy-to-size ratio for every model; this metric was a key parameter for identifying which models could be used.

Figure 16: Various models' accuracy to size ratio

Figure 17: Simplified neural network architecture

Figure 18: Alternative network architecture diagram

A CNN (Convolution Neural Network) based ML model was chosen for this time-series data, due to its lightweight and fast nature. Initially, a CNN with two or more convolution layers, which identify 8 and 16 features, respectively was tested, with an epoch of 40, batch size of 32, and 1000 steps/epoch.

After each convolution layer, a MaxPool layer was added to aggregate the information learned from the Conv2D layers. These layers shrink the size of the output tensor from the Convolution layers by picking only the largest value from the feature maps. A window size of (4, 3) was tested as the best option. Three 10% dropout layers were added to decrease overfitting during training (this layer gets rid of 10% of the data). Then this is flattened to a single 1D tensor of length 80; this is used in the Dense layers (aka Fully Connected Layers) where the NN implementation occurs. The NN has a hidden layer of 8 neurons (which was also tested as the most efficient amount) and each neuron is connected to each neuron in the layers before and after. In this way, the NN can learn the best combination of weights and biases that will produce the best results.

After plenty of experimentation, a more lightweight model with fewer feature maps in the convolution windows and less neurons proved to be more accurate, easier to train, and lighter (from 21 KB to only 7 KB).

During the training process, dozens of varying model architectures were produced. As an effective testing method, each model revision was deployed directly on the device and pre-collected crash data was fed into the model.

3.6 Model Training

To train the model, the collected data needs to first be split into training, validation, and testing (with 60%/20%/20% proportions respectively) where each crash data is represented as a Python Dictionary; the data was also labeled as either a crash or negative (no crash). The fall data (impacts or pushes to the bike while at rest) was split into 15%/5%/5% and the negative data was split into 50%/15%/15% (these two datasets were combined in the negative dataset). Due to the limited data size, the training dataset was also augmented (time warping, adding random noise, sequence shift, and movement amplification). Various amounts of augmentation was also experimented with and tested. For the data to be inputted into the input tensor, the data was then padded to achieve an input tensor length of 128, 3-axis accelerometer values; it was also shuffled into a random order to prevent bias during training, ensure random batch selection, and this also prevents the model from learning any features that might be based off the order of data. Then it was converted to a Tflite dataset, creating the input tensors.

The ratios used in splitting the data was yet another parameter that needed to be tuned to achieve optimal results. Particularly, the ideal negative data ratios were especially important as that helped the model distinguish between noise and a crash. One major problem during the training process was distinguishing between spikes in the negative data and in the crash data. Since crashes might be defined by a single spike in the data and the noisy environment generates very similar spikes, it was hard for the model to initially classify crashes.

During the training process, much experimentation : epochs, batch sizes, convolution/Max-Pool kernel sizes, steps per epoch, data augmentation amounts, data sampling (how the data is fed in), dataset sizes, and training environments (GPU and CPU). The ultimate goal was to figure out which layers and parameters had the strongest effect on predicting the correct output; this could then be used to reduce the size of the model by “shrinking” layers that “took up unnecessary

space”. The model implemented an Adam Optimizer (Adaptive Moment Estimation optimizer) and a sparse categorical cross-entropy cost function.

Figure 19: Model Accuracy graph

Figure 20: Model Loss graph

Labeled Data and in Dictionary Format

```

1 {"crash": "left_crash", "accel_ms2_xyz": [[-0.0, -0.15, -0.07], [-0.57, 0.66, 0.68], [0.33, -1.02, 1.42], [2.74, -0.32, 1.55], [0.67, -0.27, 1.62],
2 {"crash": "right_crash", "accel_ms2_xyz": [[0.85, -0.28, 0.5], [0.44, 0.08, 0.09], [-0.72, -0.29, 1.77], [0.03, -0.06, -0.14], [0.37, -0.14, 0.85],
3 {"crash": "negative", "accel_ms2_xyz": [[0.1, 0.98, -0.17], [0.1, 1.01, -0.11], [0.31, 0.95, 0.01], [0.21, 1.07, 0.17], [0.24, 0.94, 0.16], [0.3, 0
4 {"crash": "negative", "accel_ms2_xyz": [[0.42, -0.1, 0.9], [0.42, -0.1, 0.9], [0.42, -0.1, 0.9], [0.42, -0.11, 0.9], [0.42, -0.11, 0.9], [0.42, -0
5 {"crash": "negative", "accel_ms2_xyz": [[0.11, 0.02, -0.13], [-0.1, -0.44, -0.35], [-0.26, 0.01, -0.54], [-0.7, 0.34, -0.53], [-0.62, 0.62, -0.9],
6 {"crash": "negative", "accel_ms2_xyz": [[0.11, -0.96, -0.3], [0.11, -0.96, -0.3], [0.11, -0.96, -0.3], [0.11, -0.96, -0.3], [0.11, -0.96, -0.3], [0
7 {"crash": "left_crash", "accel_ms2_xyz": [[-0.02, 0.01, -0.11], [0.25, 0.07, 0.16], [1.52, -0.49, 0.15], [1.02, -0.02, 0.88], [-0.03, -0.03, 2.69],
8 {"crash": "negative", "accel_ms2_xyz": [[0.41, -0.32, 0.64], [0.42, -0.15, 0.65], [0.43, -0.09, 0.48], [0.5, -0.17, 0.42], [0.65, -0.17, 1.16], [0.
9 {"crash": "negative", "accel_ms2_xyz": [[0.88, -0.3, 1.55], [0.2, 0.3, 0.87], [0.08, -0.03, 0.3], [0.39, -0.1, 0.31], [1.33, 0.2, 0.99], [-0.47, 0.
10 {"crash": "negative", "accel_ms2_xyz": [[0.51, 0.0, 0.86], [0.54, -0.21, 0.83], [0.52, -0.08, 0.85], [0.51, -0.01, 0.86], [0.5, -0.05, 0.85], [0.5,

```

Figure 21: Example of training data structure

The final model was trained using a batch size of 64 with an epoch of 30; 1000 steps per epoch was used. The models were trained on GPUs, CPUs, and TPUs.

From the Confusion Matrix of the model after the last epoch, the Precision (TP / (TP + FP)) is 0.94 and the model has an F1 Score of 0.944.

```

Model after last epoch:
***** Evaluation test data *****
1/1 [=====] - 0s 25ms/step - loss: 0.0873 - accuracy: 0.9688
1/1 [=====] - 0s 89ms/step
tf.Tensor(
[[17  1  0  0]
 [ 1 45  0  0]
 [  0  0  0  0]
 [  0  0  0  0]], shape=(4, 4), dtype=int32)
Loss 0.0872504711151123, Accuracy 0.96875
/usr/local/lib/python3.10/dist-packages/keras/src/engine/training.py:3103: UserWarning: You are saving a model that was compiled with a different version of TensorFlow. This may result in a model that is not compatible with older versions of TensorFlow.
  saving_api.save_model(
Basic model is 7076 bytes
Quantized model is 7080 bytes
Difference is -4 bytes
*****
Model of epoch with best val_accuracy:
***** Evaluation test data *****
1/1 [=====] - 0s 23ms/step - loss: 0.2316 - accuracy: 0.9375
1/1 [=====] - 0s 20ms/step
tf.Tensor(
[[16  2  0  0]
 [ 2 44  0  0]
 [  0  0  0  0]
 [  0  0  0  0]], shape=(4, 4), dtype=int32)
Loss 0.231620192527771, Accuracy 0.9375
/usr/local/lib/python3.10/dist-packages/keras/src/engine/training.py:3103: UserWarning: You are saving a model that was compiled with a different version of TensorFlow. This may result in a model that is not compatible with older versions of TensorFlow.
  saving_api.save_model(
Basic model is 7076 bytes
Quantized model is 7080 bytes
Difference is -4 bytes

```

Figure 22: Example TensorFlow training output

4 Results and Discussion

This paper has demonstrated that relatively small (<10 KB) ML models, operating on edge devices, are capable of distinguishing features in noisy signals. It is shown that devices could be developed which can deploy these models for anomaly detection, without needing either cloud connections or resource rich hardware.

Also, it's shown that these models can be further improved to reduce their implementation footprint without hindering their accuracy. For example, I was able to reduce the final model size from over **22 KB to 7 KB**, without significantly impacting the model accuracy.

The proposed crash simulation and model testing methodologies also proved to be both cost & time efficient. As a result, I made the data that I collected in this project open-source so that others could replicate and improve this project; setting a nice foundation for proper bicycle crash detection.

It's also concluded, that for simple time-series data (e.g. just one spike in data may represent a crash), a certain number of neurons and model complexity could be used, even if there are high levels of noise. Also, for the model to properly classify crashes, it's shown that a proper selection of both negative data types and amounts helps the model properly distinguish between crashes and non-crashes.

To test the performance of ML models developed, in contrast to previous work, I compared the ML model to different statistical analysis-based models. Most of the statical-based models performed poorly in the noisy environment generated by the rough terrain. While the ML model was able to correctly identify crashes, the statistical-based model in a paper from the University of Illinois [6] struggled to detect most crashes; and a custom statistical analysis model that used ideas from [7] and [8] couldn't differentiate between crashes and falls.

After in-field testing, the accuracy of the model was obtained using $(TP+TN) / (TP + TN + FP + FN)$ where TP, TN, FP, and FN represent true positive, true negative, false positive, and false negative, respectively [3].

The ML model achieved a 99% accuracy while the custom statistical analysis model of [7] and [8] achieved 85.7% and the model of [6] achieved 71.4%.

Component	Min Consumption	Max Consumption	Typical Consumption
Boron connected to Cloud	14.6 mA	207 mA	53.4 mA
LSM9DS1 IMU at 59.5 ODR			2.4 mA
Adafruit GPS			20 mA
Total			~75.8 mA

Figure 23: Component power consumption

Item	Cost
Particle Boron LTE	\$65
LSM9DS1 9 DOF IMU	\$20
Adafruit Ultimate GPS	\$20
Other Components (Buzzer/Button)	<\$1
Total	~\$106

Figure 24: Component cost table

4.1 Push Notifications

Once a crash has been detected, the goal is to alert an emergency contact of the user's GPS location. Thus, software was added to accomplish this task, and it works in the following way: once a crash is detected, the device waits 30 seconds while sounding an alarm. The software checks to see if the button has been pressed; if it was, the Boron treats this event as a false positive, and continues with the rest of the code. However, if after the 30 second countdown the button was not pressed, the Particle Boron publishes an event on the Particle Cloud (that contains the GPS coordinates) which is then caught by a webhook. That webhook sends a request to the Push bullet web application and then sends a Push Notification to all hooked up devices (i.e. laptops, phones, etc.). The device was able to effectively transmit its GPS coordinates to an emergency contact with little delay.

Figure 25: Screenshot of received Push Notifications

4.2 Discussion and Future Research

It's shown that in the application of bicycle crash detection, containing noisy signals, ultra-lite ML models outperform statistical analysis models. So, for such feature detection tasks, an ML-based model is likely to outperform a statistical analysis based one. This has implications to a broader set of applications involving smart transportation technologies, elderly care, industrial automation, robotics, and so on.

Considering the application of detecting bicycle crashes, there are a limited number of scholarly articles that provide a statistical analysis model, a good testing methodology, and results to their models (including full data sets and software). Thus, an exact and fair comparison with such limited number of models was not feasible.

Furthermore, this project was able to simulate impacts only from the side of the test bike, since simulating head-on collisions proved to be unsafe for data collection. To overcome the budget limitations of this project, a low-cost and accurate crash simulation methodology and testbed have been developed, which are shown to be quite effective. It's recognized that crashes simulated in this project may not exactly represent bicycle crashes involving motor vehicles, nonetheless it does properly model the noise and impact environments and provides a decent baseline work for future studies.

There are multiple points that should be addressed when referring to future research on this topic. Firstly, developing various ML models that use forecasting principles to both detect and predict when anomalies will occur in the future is a promising application. Also, improving the detection algorithm to address various other features (e.g. direction of the crash; left, right, front, back). A major limitation in this study was faulty datasets, so another might be to improve the data collection methodology to more accurately represent motor-vehicle & bicycle accidents, like head-on collisions. Next, to improve the accuracy of the ML model and develop separate statistical analysis models, for comparison, to

generate more concrete results. And lastly, a more energy-efficient prototype implementation (e.g. by adding software and hardware that automatically shuts down certain devices when not in use). Finally, when trying to develop the ML model architecture, there were many limitations to the open-source library (in terms of which types of layers could be added), thus it seems like more work is required to modularize the TensorFlow for Microcontrollers library, to enable the deployment of more varying model architectures.

4.3 Collected Data | GitHub

The novel data that was collected in this study, can be found at this GitHub repository: <https://github.com/burakayy7/tinymlTestData> Test Data on GitHub

5 Conclusion

A few notable contributions include: tuning ultra-lite ML models for size reduction, without limiting model accuracy and performance, provided a development workflow and platform for data collection, model training, and testing, created a novel open-source crash dataset, and provided insights on how to tackle feature detection in noisy signals.

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